

1 Vegetation growing season dynamics across land cover classes in central 2 Europe

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24 ABSTRACT

25 Phenological shifts represent one of the most evident biological responses to climate change. This study
26 used the two-band Enhanced Vegetation Index derived from Moderate Resolution Imaging
27 Spectroradiometer satellite data to analyze changes in the growing seasons of arable land, broad-leaved
28 forest, coniferous forest, and grassland across the central European region from 2000 to 2022.
29 Phenological metrics included the start, end, and length of the growing season. Nonparametric Theil–
30 Sen regression indicated an earlier start of the season (median of trends for all land cover classes ranging
31 from -9.3 to -17.5 days per decade), a later end of the season (ranging from +8.1 to +11.4 days per
32 decade), and consequently longer length of the season (ranging from +13.3 to +25.0 days per decade),
33 with advancing SOS identified as the primary driver of LOS prolongation. The most pronounced
34 changes across all phenological metrics were associated with arable land. Elevation zone-based analysis
35 showed that the highest median of trends of start and length of the season was found for arable land and
36 coniferous forest in elevations below 600 m a.s.l., with values decreasing progressively with increasing
37 elevation. The analysis of environmental zones revealed a higher median of trends of the start and length
38 of the season in cool-moist and warm-mesic zones, while end-of-season-related changes were more
39 pronounced in cold-wet zones. This study demonstrates coherent long-term trends in vegetation
40 phenology across different land cover classes, with stronger acceleration over arable land, highlighting
41 potential implications for agricultural systems.

42 **Keywords:** land surface phenology; MODIS; EVI2; Metzger classification; phenometrics; remote
43 sensing;

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48

49 1 INTRODUCTION

50 Phenology, the study of annually recurring developmental phases of plants and animals, has been
51 documented since the 8th century, with the first European records from the 14th century
52 ([Kalvane et al. 2009](#)). This long history underlines the long-standing importance of phenology in
53 understanding climate change and its effects on vegetation. Numerous studies have shown that plant
54 phenology responds strongly to climatic drivers, particularly air temperature and photoperiod
55 (e.g., [Rafferty et al. 2020](#); [Meier et al. 2021](#); [Bartošová et al. 2022](#); [Büntgen et al. 2022](#)), but also other
56 factors such as chilling days or day length ([Menzel et al. 2020](#)). Ground-based human observations
57 remain the most accurate source of phenological information and are essential for calibrating and
58 validating models and remote sensing data. However, this method is limited by both the presence of
59 observers and their potential bias, and the spatial resolution difference, which is a limiting factor for
60 large-scale studies.

61 In recent decades, modern Earth observation techniques have enabled a shift from local point
62 observations to large-scale assessments using satellite imagery. Remote sensing platforms – including
63 visible-wavelength digital cameras with typical red, green, and blue (RGB) bands, spectral reflectance
64 sensors with multiband radiometers, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), and satellite sensors – are now
65 commonly used to monitor vegetation at national to continental scales ([Zeng et al. 2020](#)). Among remote
66 sensing products, the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MODIS) is one of the most
67 frequently used for vegetation analyses ([Caparrós-Santiago et al. 2021](#); [Siluch et al. 2022](#)).
68 Vegetation phenology information derived from such data is commonly referred to as land surface
69 phenology (LSP). LSP observations are commonly based on vegetation indices (VIs) ([Caparrós-
70 Santiago et al. 2021](#)), which integrate information from two or more spectral bands that are generally
71 sensitive to different plant characteristics (e.g., water content, leaf area or plant pigments)
72 ([Zeng et al. 2020](#)). The most frequently used VIs include the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
73 (NDVI) ([Rouse 1973](#)), the Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) ([Huete et al. 1999](#)), and the two-band
74 Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI2) ([Caparrós-Santiago et al. 2021](#)). The EVI2 is derived from the EVI
75 that retains the soil-noise adjustment and improves sensitivity in areas with high biomass (similar to the
76 EVI) but without the need to use the blue band ([Jiang et al. 2008](#)). These indices allow the extraction of
77 key phenological metrics (phenometrics), including the start (SOS), end (EOS), and length (LOS) of the
78 growing season, which are used to assess changes in vegetation phenology ([Caparrós-
79 Santiago et al. 2021](#)).

80 Both ground-based ([Meier et al. 2021](#); [Büntgen et al. 2022](#)) and remote sensing studies ([Bhutto et
81 al. 2019](#); [Garonna et al. 2014](#); [Li et al. 2019b](#); [Zhao et al. 2015](#)) have previously indicated that the
82 growing season has lengthened due to earlier spring onset and delayed autumn dormancy. Studies
83 focusing on the changes in the vegetation season relative to elevation ([Lukasová et al. 2020](#); [Kern et al.
84 2020](#)) or environmental areas ([Royo et al. 2014](#); [Li et al. 2019b](#)) deepen this knowledge with respect to
85 not only time but also space. What is often lacking in traditional *in situ* studies are spatial factors (e.g.,
86 landscape-level spatial variability), which are made available by the use of remote sensing observations.
87 However, many studies assess phenometrics separately—frequently focusing only on SOS—preventing
88 evaluation of LOS, which requires both SOS and EOS ([Siluch et al. 2022](#)). Moreover, few studies have
89 focused on multiple land cover classes (LCCs), underscoring the need to investigate whether different
90 vegetation types show distinct long-term patterns in growing-season timing and duration.

91 Understanding whether different vegetation types exhibit specific long-term patterns in the timing
92 and duration of the growing season is key to interpreting ecosystem responses to climate and land cover
93 changes. We hypothesize that the timing and duration of the growing season have changed differently
94 for arable lands, grasslands, and forested areas, reflecting their distinct vegetation dynamics and
95 interactions with environmental drivers. Therefore, the objectives of the present study are (1) to establish
96 phenometrics (SOS, EOS, LOS) based on the Enhanced Vegetation Index 2 (EVI2) for individual land
97 cover classes (arable land, AL; broad-leaved forest, BF; coniferous forest, CF; grassland, GL) for the
98 period 2000–2022 in central Europe; (2) to analyze trends and the rate of change in the timing of the

99 growing season defined by the selected phenometrics for each class; and (3) to determine changes in
100 phenometrics (SOS, EOS, LOS) across five elevation zones and eight environmental zones (based on
101 the Metzger classification) for each land cover class.

102 Phenometrics were derived using a simplified threshold-based method, in which a fixed EVI2
103 value of 0.3 was used to determine the start and end of the growing season. Threshold-based methods
104 are widely used in phenological research ([Caparros-Santiago et al. 2021](#)), and this approach prioritizes
105 robustness and temporal-spatial consistency over region-specific calibration and allows for efficient
106 comparison across different years and locations. Despite its simplicity, this method captures dominant
107 patterns of vegetation development, particularly in agricultural landscapes. Moreover, White et al.
108 ([2014](#)) demonstrated that a fixed EVI threshold of 0.3 provides a robust approximation of full leaf-out
109 in temperate forests, supporting the use of threshold-based methods for large-scale phenological
110 assessments. Although EVI2 differs from the original EVI formulation by omitting the blue band, it
111 retains similar seasonal dynamics and scaling properties. Exploratory analyses of aggregated EVI2 time
112 series in our study area confirmed that this value consistently marks the transition to the main vegetation
113 growth phase.

114 In this study, we analyze long-term EVI2 time series spanning more than two decades (2000–
115 2022) to investigate vegetation seasonality across central Europe. Our approach enables spatially
116 consistent comparisons among land cover classes, elevation zones, and environmental regions. By
117 addressing outlined objectives, the study aims to provide new insights into how different land cover
118 types and environmental gradients shape long-term trends in vegetation phenology.

119 **2 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

120 *2.1 Study area and type of vegetation*

121 This LSP study was conducted in central Europe, with the area being defined by the following
122 coordinates: top, left: 55.62, 0.44; and bottom, right: 33.96, 39.71 (Fig. 1). Within this area, four LCCs
123 were determined (AL, BF, CF, GL) and analyzed according to the SOS, EOS, and LOS in the time
124 period from 2000–2022.

125 For the classification of land cover, we primarily relied on the Corine Land Cover (CLC) dataset,
126 version 16 (04/2012) with a spatial resolution of 250 m, which offers a well-established and widely used
127 classification scheme across Europe. Compared to other global products, such as GlobCover, CLC
128 provides more detailed and unambiguous thematic classes, which makes it more suitable for
129 distinguishing the land cover categories analyzed in this study (arable land, grassland, broad-leaved
130 forest, coniferous forest).

131 However, the CLC database covers only 81% of the land area in the study domain. The ESA-
132 GlobCover Land Cover Product ([2005](#)) at a spatial resolution of $1/360^\circ$ (pixel size of approximately 280
133 m in the study area) was used to fill in the gaps. Both datasets were resampled and snapped to the spatial
134 resolution of the satellite vegetation data, i.e., 250 m, using the Spatial Analyst extension of ArcGIS
135 software (Geographical Information System). Subsequently, they were reclassified based on the
136 majority of contiguous neighboring cells into 10 basic types: (1) arable land; (2) heterogeneous
137 agricultural areas; (3) grassland and pastures; (4) broad-leaved forest; (5) coniferous forest; (6) mixed
138 forest; (7) scrub and/or herbaceous vegetation associations and/or bare areas; (8) artificial surfaces; (9)
139 water bodies; and (10) wetlands. This harmonization into a unified classification scheme reduces
140 inconsistencies between CLC and GlobCover landcover datasets.

141 *2.2 Remote sensing data*

142 For vegetation monitoring, we used daily image data from the MODIS sensor that was carried on
143 the polar-orbiting Terra satellite, specifically the MOD09GQ product (available through the LP DAAC
144 Data Pool; [Vermote and Wolfe 2015](#)), which provides atmospherically corrected surface reflectance in
145 the red and near-infrared bands at 250 m spatial resolution with daily temporal coverage. The remote
146 sensing data were first filtered to remove low-quality observations caused by clouds, snow, or

147 atmospheric disturbances. For this purpose, the per-pixel quality flags provided in the MOD09GQ
148 product were used as a logical mask applied to the reflectance bands. Only pixels classified as highest
149 overall quality according to the overall quality flag (bits 0–1) were retained for further processing.
150 Subsequently, the EVI2 vegetation index was calculated as follows:

$$\text{EVI2} = G \frac{\rho\text{NIR} - \rho\text{Red}}{\rho\text{NIR} + \left(6 - \frac{7.5}{c}\right)\rho\text{Red} + 1} \quad (1)$$

151 where G is the gain factor (2,5). ρRed and ρNIR are the reflectance values in the red and near-infrared
152 (NIR) bands, respectively. c is derived by linearly fitting $\rho\text{Red} = c \times \rho\text{NIR}$ ([Jiang et al. 2008](#)).

153 Although the quality of the input reflectance data was improved using the MODIS quality flags,
154 some residual noise remained. To reduce this high-frequency variability in the EVI2 time series, we
155 applied an additional filtering procedure. The raw EVI2 values derived from the satellite sensor were
156 examined within a ± 7 -day moving window, where each daily value was compared against the weighted
157 average of that period. Outliers were identified when the relative deviation for a specific day exceeded
158 the range from -0.5 to $+1.5$ standard deviations (SD) from the long-term distribution and were
159 subsequently removed. Asymmetric thresholds of -0.5 and $+1.5$ standard deviations were applied to
160 reduce short-term negative fluctuations in the EVI2 signal while allowing positive deviations that remain
161 consistent with typical seasonal vegetation dynamics. Missing values were then reconstructed using
162 linear temporal interpolation.

163 The EVI2 time series used in this study originates from an operational drought-monitoring
164 framework. This framework was intentionally applied without modification in order to preserve
165 temporal consistency and spatial comparability across the full study period and region. Although the
166 database was not originally developed for phenological analysis, the applied quality filtering and
167 temporal smoothing yield stable and spatially continuous information on vegetation activity, which is
168 suitable for detecting long-term changes in vegetation season dynamics.

169 Phenometrics were derived from the preprocessed EVI2 time series using a fixed threshold-based
170 approach. We focused on three key phenometrics: SOS, EOS, and LOS. The SOS and EOS were first
171 determined for each 250 m pixel within the four LCC (AL, GL, BF, CF). SOS was defined as the first
172 day of the year (DOY) when the EVI2 value exceeded 0.3, restricted to $\text{DOY} < 152$. EOS was defined
173 as the first DOY when the index value fell below 0.3, constrained to occur between DOY 213 (the
174 earliest date) and 334 (the latest date). LOS was then calculated as the difference between EOS and
175 SOS.

176 To obtain spatially robust estimates and to eliminate the variability caused by the crop rotation
177 schemes and changing crop patterns across seasons, the pixel-level SOS and EOS values were
178 aggregated to the 5×5 km grid level. Only pixels belonging to the dominant LCC within each grid were
179 considered, and a valid SOS/EOS estimate required that at least 75 % of these pixels crossed the
180 threshold. The representative SOS and EOS for each grid were then calculated as the average of the
181 mode and median of the pixel-level dates, which minimizes the influence of outliers while preserving
182 the most typical timing. Aggregation minimizes the influence of local heterogeneity and mapping
183 uncertainties, thereby ensuring temporal and spatial comparability across the study domain. In total, the
184 study area comprised 112,837 grids. After assigning LCCs, analyses were performed with 91,440 grid
185 cells for AL, 82,602 for BF, 55,473 for CF, and 79,068 for GL (Table S1).

186 2.3 Analysis of phenometric trends

187 To quantify long-term changes in phenological metrics (SOS, EOS, LOS), annual average values
188 were first calculated for each land cover class (LCC) over the study period (2000–2022). Trends were
189 then estimated using the non-parametric Theil–Sen regression ([Theil 1950](#); [Sen 1968](#)), with the slope
190 representing the rate of change per year. Statistical significance was evaluated using the Mann–Kendall
191 test ([Mann 1945](#); [Kendall and Gibbons 1990](#)), with three levels of significance reported: * significant
192 trend at $\alpha = 0.05$; ** significant trend at $\alpha = 0.01$; *** significant trend at $\alpha = 0.001$. This statistical

193 method was used in all the analyses of the phenometric trends. Trend analysis was performed with the
194 R 4.2.2 programming language ([R Core Team 2022](#)).

195 For a more detailed analysis of the changes in the phenometric trends, the SOS, EOS, and LOS
196 trends were calculated for each available 5×5 km grid and each LCC separately. The aggregated results
197 of the trend analysis were represented by the median of the trends of all the grids for each LCC and each
198 phenometric. The median of the trends was used due to the large number of grids and to limit the
199 influence of extreme values that could be included in the average of the trends. Furthermore, the trends
200 for each 5×5 km grid were visualized as maps. These maps included visualizations for each
201 phenometric: the values of the grids with statistically significant trends based on the p-value and a level
202 of significance of $\alpha = 0.05$.

203 To assess whether the phenological trends differed with elevation, all the calculated SOS, EOS,
204 and LOS trends for the individual LCCs for each available 5×5 km grid (calculated in the second set
205 of analyses) were divided into five elevation zones with a maximum elevation of 1500 m. The elevation
206 zones were divided into 300 m intervals—i.e., 0–300, 300–600, 600–900, 900–1200 and 1200–
207 1500 m a.s.l. (Fig. 1b). The elevation was calculated for each 5×5 km grid based on Digital Elevation
208 Model - SRTM 4.1 (CGIAR-CSI), which has a 250 m resolution. The mean elevation for each 5×5 km
209 grid was used to divide the area into elevation zones. The results of the trend analysis for each elevation
210 zone were also represented by the median of the trends of all the grids for each LCC and each
211 phenometric.

212 Finally, to assess whether the phenological trends differed among environmental conditions, all
213 the SOS, EOS, and LOS trends for the individual LCCs for each available 5×5 km grid (calculated in
214 the second set of analyses) were divided into environmental zones using Metzger's classification
215 ([Metzger 2018](#)). Since Metzger's classification covers the entire world and includes environmental
216 zones that are not present in central Europe, we selected only zones intersecting our study area, resulting
217 in eight classes: extremely cold and wet; cold and wet; extremely cold and mesic; cold and mesic; cool
218 temperate and dry; cool temperate and xeric; cool temperate and moist; warm temperate and mesic; and
219 warm temperate and xeric (Fig. 1c). The results of the trend analysis for each Metzger classification
220 zone were also represented by the median of the trends of all the grids for each LCC and each
221 phenometric.

222 To ensure robust estimates, in the trend analyses of elevation zones and Metzger environmental
223 zones, only categories that contained at least 100 grids were evaluated. LCC–zone combinations that
224 did not meet this minimum sample size threshold were excluded from the trend evaluation. For example,
225 AL occurred in fewer than 100 grids in the extremely cold and wet environmental zone, and therefore,
226 trends could not be assessed for this LCC in that zone.

227 **3 RESULTS**

228 *3.1 Overall average trends*

229 The annual average of all the available grids within each LCC was evaluated (Fig. 2). The
230 phenometrics analysis showed the overall highest average trends for AL for all the evaluated
231 phenometrics (SOS = -9.6 days per decade, EOS = +7.6 days per decade, and LOS = +17.7 days per
232 decade, Fig. 2). Lower values were observed for BF, CF, and GL, but the trends were consistent:
233 negative trends (a shift to an earlier date) in the SOS, positive trends (a shift to a later date) in the EOS,
234 and positive trends (a prolongation of the vegetation season) in the LOS (Fig. 2).

235 *3.2 Spatial distribution and magnitude of trends*

236 Trends were calculated individually for each grid, LCC, and phenometric. Grids with statistically
237 significant negative trends in SOS were mainly concentrated in the western and southern parts of the
238 study area (Fig. 3). Conversely, the eastern and northeastern regions were dominated by grid cells with
239 statistically significant positive trends in the EOS (Fig. 3). This spatial pattern—negative SOS trends in

240 some areas and positive EOS trends in others—resulted in most grid cells exhibiting a positive LOS trend
241 across the entire study area for all LCCs (Fig. 3).

242 The results also showed areas with opposite trends (mainly in SOS and LOS and distributed
243 mostly in the eastern part of the area) or no trends (mainly in EOS and distributed mostly in the western
244 or central part of the area) for all the phenometrics. However, the percentage of these grids was low and
245 ranged from 0.2 to 4.9% of all statistically significant grids for each LCC (Table S1).

246 Beyond the observed spatial distribution of trends, the results at the LCC level showed consistent
247 shifts in phenometrics across all land cover classes. AL showed the most pronounced medians of
248 statistically significant trends for all phenometrics (Table S2). The highest median of statistically
249 significant trends was found for the LOS, and this positive trend ranged from +13.3 to +25.0 days per
250 decade (Table S2); moreover, the highest percentage of significant grids, which ranged from 33.1% to
251 55.4%, was detected for the LOS and all the LCCs (Table S1).

252 Across all LCCs, in grid cells where both SOS and EOS exhibited statistically significant trends,
253 a larger proportion of those grids showed stronger SOS trends than EOS trends, indicating that LOS
254 prolongation in these areas was primarily driven by SOS rather than EOS. The percentage of SOS-driven
255 grid cells ranged from 8.8% to 16.9% from all available statistically significant LOS grid cells for each
256 LCC. In contrast, the proportion of EOS-driven grid cells was consistently lower, ranging from 7.6% to
257 11.1%. In addition, across all LCCs, the results showed that grids with statistically nonsignificant
258 negative trends in the SOS or statistically nonsignificant positive trends in the EOS (or both) resulted in
259 statistically significant positive trends in the LOS. This relationship was most pronounced in the BF
260 (82.0% of the grids from all statistically significant LOS grids). In the case of AL, CF, and GL, this
261 percentage was lower but still high, ranging from 68.1% to 77.6%.

262 3.3 *Elevation-dependent patterns of phenological trends*

263 Because previous results from Section 3.2 showed that even nonsignificant SOS/EOS trends can
264 lead to significant LOS trends, all grid cells were evaluated regardless of statistical significance. Across
265 all elevation zones, the highest median trends were detected for LOS, with positive values ranging from
266 +5.3 to +15.7 days per decade (Table S3). The contribution of individual phenometrics to LOS
267 lengthening varied among LCCs and across elevation zones. For AL, CF, and GL, the median of
268 negative SOS trends was the primary driver of LOS lengthening in all elevation zones. In contrast, the
269 median of positive EOS trends was detected across all elevation zones only for BF and CF and in case
270 of BF mostly influenced LOS lengthening (Fig. 4). The influence of EOS was particularly limited in
271 AL, where positive EOS trends occurred only in the lowlands (0–300 m a.s.l.) and were equal to zero in
272 all higher elevation zones. For GL, the median of EOS trends was equal to zero across all elevation
273 zones. In the lowland and midland zones (0–300 and 300–600 m a.s.l., respectively), SOS played a
274 major role in LOS prolongation for most of the LCCs. At higher elevations, however, negative SOS
275 trends and positive LOS trends became less pronounced, indicating a gradual decrease in these trends
276 with increasing elevation (Fig. 4).

277 3.4 *Environment-zone-dependent patterns of phenological trends*

278 The division of grids according to the Metzger environmental zones showed that LOS exhibited
279 the highest median trends across all LCCs and zones, with positive values ranging from +6.3 to +21.4
280 days per decade (Table S4). In the moist and warm zones (cool temperate and moist; warm temperate
281 and mesic), LOS prolongation showed a uniformly SOS-driven pattern across all LCCs, with the
282 strongest effects observed in AL (Fig. 5). These environmental zones were located mostly in the
283 southern and southeastern parts of the study area and corresponded largely to the lower elevation zones
284 (0–600 m), consistent with earlier findings of this study showing stronger SOS and LOS trends in these
285 regions.

286 In contrast, in the colder environmental zones (extremely cold and wet; cold and wet; extremely
287 cold and mesic), situated predominantly above 600 m, LOS prolongation was mainly driven by positive
288 EOS trends for all LCCs except AL, which did not occur in these zones. For BF and CF, a notable

289 influence of positive EOS trends on LOS was also detected in the cold and mesic, cool temperate and
290 dry, and cool temperate and xeric zones. In these three zones, LOS prolongation in AL and GL was
291 primarily driven by negative SOS trends, except in AL in the cool temperate and dry zone, where EOS
292 had a stronger influence. These environmental zones covered large portions of the western,
293 northwestern, northern, and northeastern parts of the study area, where the influence of SOS or EOS on
294 LOS varied both spatially and among LCCs.

295 Due to an insufficient number of grid cells in several environmental zones, it was not possible to
296 evaluate all LCCs across all zones. In the extremely cold and wet zone, only GL contained enough grids
297 for evaluation, whereas in the warm temperate and xeric zone this was the case only for AL. For AL,
298 grid numbers were also insufficient in the cold and wet zone and in the extremely cold and mesic zone,
299 and trends could not be assessed in these zones. In Fig. 5, the other missing columns represent LCC–
300 zone combinations in which the median of trends was equal to zero.

301 4 DISCUSSION

302 Using a simplified fixed-threshold approach originally developed for drought monitoring, we
303 identified long-term trends in the start (SOS), end (EOS), and length (LOS) of the growing season that
304 differed systematically between land cover classes (LCCs) (arable land–AL; broad-leaved forest–BF;
305 coniferous forest–CF; and grassland–GL) and environmental gradients. Compared to land surface
306 phenology (LSP) studies, our analysis is unique in that it simultaneously evaluated three key
307 phenometrics across four LCCs over a large central European region and a 23-year period (2000–2022).

308 Earlier studies mainly focused on smaller areas, fewer vegetation types, or single phenometrics
309 (e.g., SOS-only analyses) (Siluch et al. 2022). For example, Fu et al. (2014) examined only SOS in
310 western Central Europe, whereas Tian et al. (2021) evaluated SOS and EOS solely for forests and
311 grasslands. Our study, therefore, addressed a gap in LSP research, which has primarily targeted natural
312 ecosystems (e.g., Kern et al. 2020; Lukasová et al. 2020) and spring phenology, with limited attention
313 to agricultural landscapes, multi-LCC comparisons, or whole LOS (Hassan et al. 2024).

314 The overall trend analysis, based on the average of all grid cells for each phenometric, revealed
315 statistically significant advances in SOS and delays in EOS, resulting in a prolongation of LOS across
316 all LCCs. These patterns were consistent with the grid cell-level analyses, which likewise showed
317 predominantly negative SOS trends and positive EOS and LOS trends regardless of statistical
318 significance. The spring season is among the most widely investigated parts of vegetation phenology
319 (Hassan et al. 2024), and the earlier SOS detected in our study corresponded with findings from both
320 ground-based observations (e.g., Menzel et al. 2020; Meier et al. 2021; Bartošová et al. 2025) and
321 satellite-derived analyses (e.g., Jeong et al. 2011; Bellini et al. 2023). Although EOS and LOS have been
322 investigated less frequently than SOS, existing studies also report delayed EOS and prolonged LOS,
323 which is consistent with our findings (e.g., for EOS: Jeong et al. 2011; Liu et al. 2016; Zhang et al. 2022;
324 and for LOS: Garonna et al. 2014; Guo et al. 2021).

325 Our results revealed clear differences in both the magnitude and spatial distribution of trends
326 among phenometrics and LCCs. LOS exhibited the highest changes across all LCCs, in agreement with
327 previous studies (Garonna et al. 2014; Park et al. 2016; Guo et al. 2021). The consistent dominance of
328 advancing SOS as the main driver of LOS prolongation across different vegetation types highlights a
329 robust, cross-LCC response, confirming SOS as a key control of seasonal extension (Shen et al. 2015;
330 Park et al. 2016; Ontel et al. 2025). In our study, the advance of SOS was most pronounced in AL, a
331 pattern consistent with recent ground-based phenological observations, which reported stronger spring
332 advances in agricultural areas than in more natural LCCs (Bartošová et al. 2025). This pronounced shift
333 in AL is likely related to agricultural management practices, which increasingly favor earlier sowing
334 dates in spring to optimize soil moisture availability and reduce exposure to summer droughts. Under
335 ongoing climate change, European agriculture is expected to experience altered climatic conditions that
336 affect the timing and length of periods suitable for farming, thereby requiring adaptive management
337 strategies (Trnka et al. 2011), a pattern supported by the trends observed here. The strongest SOS

338 advances in AL were concentrated in the southern and southeastern parts of the study area, where
339 reduced spring soil moisture may further constrain sowing windows and intensify management-driven
340 phenological shifts (Trnka et al. 2011). While LCC-specific differences in trend magnitudes can partly
341 be attributed to environmental conditions, the influence of human activity during the spring season
342 appears particularly pronounced in AL (e.g., Menzel et al. 2020 or Guo et al. 2021).

343 Although SOS dominated LOS prolongation across all LCCs in our study, EOS also contributed
344 to changes in the growing season. Previous studies have shown that autumn phenology can play a
345 dominant role for specific land cover types, such as forests or grasslands (Liu et al., 2016; Guo et al.,
346 2021), or in particular regions (Garonna et al., 2014; Zhao et al., 2015; Švik et al. 2025). Moreover,
347 Jeong et al. (2011) reported that the contribution of EOS to LOS prolongation increased after 2000
348 compared with the earlier period of 1982–1999, indicating a growing importance of autumn phenology
349 in recent decades. Overall, our findings support the view that while EOS can contribute to LOS
350 prolongation, especially for specific land covers or areas, spring phenology remains the primary driver
351 of long-term changes in the growing season. These results highlight the need for further investigation of
352 EOS dynamics, which remain less explored than spring phenology, largely due to the limited availability
353 of ground-based autumn phenological observations.

354 Furthermore, our results showed that only a limited proportion of grid cells exhibited statistically
355 significant trends, while grids with statistically nonsignificant SOS or EOS trends could nevertheless
356 display statistically significant LOS trends. This occurs because LOS integrates changes at both the start
357 and end of the growing season, such that small, individually nonsignificant shifts in SOS and EOS can
358 combine to produce a significant change in LOS. This indicates that nonsignificant shifts in SOS or EOS
359 should not be dismissed, as their combined effect can still represent a meaningful response of vegetation
360 phenology to climate change (Švik et al. 2025).

361 One methodological limitation of this study should be acknowledged. The use of a fixed EVI2
362 threshold (0.3) across all land cover classes simplifies the complex and diverse dynamics of vegetation
363 phenology. Rather than representing exact biological phenophases, this threshold captures the dominant
364 phase of seasonal vegetation activity in an operational sense.

365 The spatial patterns of phenological trends exhibited clear regional differentiation across the study
366 area. Grids with advancing SOS were mainly concentrated in the western and southern parts, whereas
367 delayed EOS were more prevalent in the eastern and northeastern regions. Positive LOS trends were
368 widespread and occurred across most of the study area, reflecting the combined influence of shifts in
369 both spring and autumn phenology. The spatial distribution of advancing SOS is consistent with large-
370 scale temperature gradients across Europe. Doshi et al. (2023) reported increasing spring temperatures
371 from southern to central Europe, extending across both western and eastern regions, with maximum
372 temperatures occurring progressively later in the season toward northern Europe. Such temperature
373 patterns likely contribute to earlier spring onset in the southern and western parts of the study area,
374 where spring warming is more pronounced.

375 In addition to these dominant spatial patterns, we also identified grid cells exhibiting contrasting
376 trends, such as delayed SOS or advancing EOS. However, these grid cells represented only a small
377 proportion of the evaluated area across all LCCs and did not alter the overall regional patterns. Such
378 spatial heterogeneity in phenological responses has been reported only rarely in the literature
379 (Hassan et al. 2024). Comparable patterns of co-occurring advances and delays in SOS and EOS have
380 been documented, for example, in Pakistan (Bhutto et al. 2019) and across parts of the Northern
381 Hemisphere (Liu et al. 2016). In line with our findings, these studies reported the coexistence of
382 opposing trends but primarily emphasized the dominant patterns in their conclusions. While such
383 contrasting trends may reflect local-scale variability related to environmental conditions or land
384 management, their limited spatial extent suggests that they represent marginal deviations rather than a
385 systematic phenological response.

386 The elevation-based analysis showed that phenological trends were strongest at lower elevations,
387 particularly below 600 m a.s.l., and generally weakened with increasing elevation across all LCCs.
388 However, this elevation-dependent weakening was evident primarily for SOS and LOS. Air temperature

389 is one of the key climatic drivers of phenological change, and with increasing elevation, temperatures
390 decrease, while precipitation often increases (Lukasová et al. 2019). These gradients likely explain the
391 observed patterns and are consistent with previous studies from Slovakia (Schrieber 2014) and across
392 Europe (Belliny et al. 2023), which reported the earliest SOS at the lowest elevations, followed by a
393 progressive delay with increasing elevation. In our study, SOS trends primarily drove the LOS
394 prolongation of AL, CF, and GL. In contrast, EOS trends exhibited greater heterogeneity and no clear
395 elevational gradient. Their contribution to LOS changes was most evident in forested LCCs (BF and
396 CF), whereas EOS played only a minor role in AL and GL across most elevation zones. Overall, these
397 results suggest that phenological responses to elevation are LCC-specific and that autumn phenology is
398 governed by different and more complex controls than spring phenology, highlighting the need for
399 further research on EOS drivers along elevational gradients.

400 The environment-zone-based analysis further demonstrated that LOS was the most responsive
401 phenometric across all land cover classes and environmental zones, confirming its sensitivity to the
402 combined effects of spring and autumn phenological changes. In warm-mesic and cool-moist temperate
403 zones, LOS prolongation was consistently driven by advancing SOS across all LCCs, with the strongest
404 responses observed in AL. This pattern aligns with earlier results of this study based on spatial and
405 elevational gradients, which showed that warmer lowland regions exhibit more pronounced spring
406 advances and growing-season extensions. The concentration of these environmental zones in the
407 southern and southeastern parts of the study area suggests that temperature-driven spring processes play
408 a key role in shaping phenological responses under favorable climatic conditions, particularly in
409 agriculturally managed landscapes. This regional differentiation is consistent with earlier large-scale
410 observations of phenological gradients across Europe. Badeck et al. (2004) reported earlier spring green-
411 up in mild oceanic regions of southwestern Europe and progressively later SOS toward colder
412 continental regions in northeastern Europe, supporting the strong SOS-driven patterns observed in warm
413 and mesic zones in our study. In contrast, colder and wetter environmental zones exhibited a relatively
414 stronger influence of EOS on LOS dynamics. More pronounced EOS-related changes were detected
415 mainly for BF, CF, and GL in extremely cold and wet, cold and wet, and extremely cold and mesic
416 zones, largely corresponding to Alpine, Balkan, and Carpathian regions above 900 m a.s.l. This pattern
417 is consistent with the findings of Liu et al. (2016), who reported a higher sensitivity of autumn phenology
418 in colder environments. Overall, the environment-zone-based analysis highlights that phenological
419 controls on LOS vary across climatic contexts, with spring processes dominating in warm lowland
420 regions and autumn processes gaining relative importance in colder and high-elevation environments.
421 The use of Metzger's environmental zones thus provides a robust framework for interpreting large-scale
422 phenological variability beyond individual climatic drivers.

423 An additional insight emerged for GL at high elevations. The environmental zone analysis
424 revealed pronounced EOS trends for GL in the extremely cold and wet zone, which predominantly
425 occurs at elevations above 1500 m a.s.l. These elevation ranges were not included in the general
426 elevation-based analysis because other LCCs were largely absent there. However, owing to the sufficient
427 number of GL grid cells in these high-elevation zones, we conducted a complementary elevation
428 analysis focusing exclusively on GL and EOS. This analysis revealed markedly stronger EOS trends
429 above 1500 m a.s.l. (Fig. S1), indicating enhanced autumn sensitivity of GL. This finding is consistent
430 with previous studies showing that alpine grasslands at higher elevations respond more strongly to
431 climate variability than those at lower elevations (Li et al. 2019a).

432 Taken together, these results show that phenological responses across Central Europe are strongly
433 modulated by land cover, elevation, and environmental context. While spring phenology dominates
434 growing season changes in warm lowland regions, autumn processes gain importance in colder and
435 high-elevation environments. This integrated perspective helps to place the observed phenological
436 trends into a broader climatic and ecological context.

437 5 CONCLUSIONS

438 Our study revealed clear spatial differences in the timing of the growing season of LCCs under
439 varying environmental conditions in the central European region over the past two decades. The most
440 pronounced changes were the negative SOS trends and the positive LOS trends for AL, particularly in
441 lower-elevation zones and southern, warmer regions, with advancing SOS identified as the primary
442 driver of LOS prolongation. We concluded that these changes likely reflect both the advance of climatic
443 warming and spring agricultural management practices.

444 In addition, our results showed that SOS and/or EOS trends lacking statistical significance can
445 still contribute to significant changes in LOS and thus represent meaningful vegetation responses to
446 climate change. Despite the inherent methodological constraints, our study demonstrates that
447 operationally collected vegetation index data can reveal meaningful patterns of seasonal change. The
448 observed differences among land cover classes highlight the importance of tailored approaches in
449 phenological monitoring and point to the need for more detailed, process-oriented studies.

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612 **Figures**

614 **Fig. 1** A map of the analyzed area in central Europe (a). Division of the study area into elevation zones
615 (b). Division of the study area into Metzger classification zones (c). Map lines delineate study areas and
616 do not necessarily depict accepted national boundaries

617

618 **Fig. 2** Average Theil–Sen trends and Mann–Kendall p-values (p) of the start of the growing season
 619 (SOS), the end of the growing season (EOS), and the length of the growing season (LOS) from all
 620 available grids corresponding to arable land (AL), broad-leaved forest (BF), coniferous forest (CF) and
 621 grassland (GL) in the period from 2000 to 2022. * Significant trend at $\alpha = 0.05$; ** significant trend at
 622 $\alpha = 0.01$; *** significant trend at $\alpha = 0.001$

623

624 **Fig. 3** Spatial distributions of the trends (days per decade) of statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) grids
 625 for the start of the growing season (SOS), the end of the growing season (EOS), and for the length of
 626 the growing season (LOS) for arable land (AL), broad-leaved forest (BF), coniferous forest (CF), and
 627 grassland (GL). Map lines delineate study areas and do not necessarily depict accepted national
 628 boundaries

629

630 **Fig. 4** Median of trends (days per decade) in all available grids for the start of the growing season (SOS),
 631 the end of the growing season (EOS), and the length of the growing season (LOS) in five elevation zones
 632 with 300 m a.s.l. intervals. Brown represents arable land (AL), light green represents broad-leaved forest
 633 (BF), dark green represents coniferous forest (CF), and yellow represents grassland (GL)

634

635 **Fig. 5** Median of trends (days per decade) in all the available grids for the start of the growing season
 636 (SOS), the end of the growing season (EOS), and the length of the growing season (LOS) sorted by the
 637 Metzger classification zones. Brown represents arable land (AL), light green represents broad-leaved
 638 forest (BF), dark green represents coniferous forest (CF), and yellow represents grassland (GL)